

TEACHING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN TO UZBEK FOLK DANCE ELEMENTS

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of teaching preschool children to Uzbek folk dance elements in the musical education of preschool children, the goals and objectives of teaching it to children, and the expected results.

Keywords: dance, rhythmic movements, "Surnay lazgi", "Dutor lazgi", "Qayroq lazgi", "Garmon lazgi", dance costumes.

Today, one of the most important tasks before preschool educational organizations is to educate the younger generation, which is the future of our country, as a harmonious generation. The role of music training in preschool educational organizations is great in raising children both spiritually and physically healthy. Especially musical rhythmic movements and Dance Activities, which are one of the main activities of music training, are of great importance in this regard.

In the rhythmic movements and dance part of musical education, children learn to move in pairs, at the same time, move according to the content of the song, Move in accordance with the melody of the music, clap in accordance with the melody, clumping legs, rotating fingers, accurately perform slightly complex dance movements starting from simple dance elements, move in pairs, move according to the

In the process of performing musical rhythmic movements and teaching dance movements, various music, songs are widely used. Together with the works created by compazitors for Children, national folk melodies and songs are addressed. Especially, "Asp bo'laman", "Do'loncha", "Yallama yorim", "Qari navo", "Chitti gul", "Chertmak", "Ufor", "Andijon polkasi", "Jonon", "Namanganning olmasi", "Olma pishganda keling" Uzbek folk songs and songs are widely used.

Today, in addition to our national songs highlighted above, it is also of particular importance to teach children to dance to "Khorezm lazgisi". Because, one of the dances that is the most beautiful and truly gives pleasure to a person, glorifying nationality - "Lazgi".

The inclusion of the dance "Lazgi" in the representative list of UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage of humanity on December 12, 2019 indicates that

it is a rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people. This means that teaching the younger generation of our national cultural heritage, recognized by the world today, is an important task of every music leader.

Our practical experience of several years shows that in preschool educational organizations, teaching lazgi dance is of particular importance in increasing the musical education of children. The purpose of teaching it and the expected results are as follows:

- in the process of performing dance movements to the lazgi melody, a musical talent, rhythmic sense of children are formed;
- helps to concentrate, strengthen the memory of the child;
- due to the fact that lazgi Kui is performed at a fast pace, it helps children to be mobile, agile;
- the initial Khorezm in children forms dance skills typical of the local style;
- affects the plasticity of the child's body and the correct growth of his figure;
- The colorful tones of lazgi melody, such as " Surnay lazgi", " Dutor lazgi", " sad lazgi", " Garmon lazgi", firstly, will help children get acquainted with national musical instruments, and secondly, the timbre reading will develop well in children;
 - national dances give children an upbeat mood. It evokes various emotional sensations, giving the child freshness and enthusiasm;
 - through the lazgi dance, children get to know our national dances, which are our spiritual heritage, and receive spiritual nutrients from them;
 - the use of lazgi melody in musical education forms creativity in children. In IT, children create a "new dance " by choosing action elements that match the character of the music through their skills and skills from music lessons;
 - the variety of specific costumes of our national dances also increases interest in dance art in children. Especially children are attracted by the dresses typical of the Khorezm dance school, which are worn in lazgi dance. Because Khorezm dancers harir kuylak and must wear misak (munisak) over them, shiny on their heads, and tangachali Takha (skullcap). They wear jewelry - shovkala (shokila), bite (zirak), rust (rustle). The dancers, on the other hand, wear yaktey (yaktak), dun, adik (boots) on the leg, a maid on the head. Dresses with bright colors, jewelry with glitter and a unique sound will not go unnoticed by any child. Children who have come up with and put on such dresses try to thoroughly study and perform the lazgi dance and imagine themselves as if they were real dancers;

-in almost all festive evenings, such as “Navruz”, “mother's day”, “Hayr kindergarten”, which are held in preschool educational organizations, Lazgi dance gives a festive mood to everyone with its playfulness. It is for this reason that it is advisable for music leaders to include this dance in the repertoire of festive mornings;

- performing dance movements helps children grow mentally and physically healthy.

At this point, let's briefly touch on the order in which the Lazgi dance movements are performed. The dance begins with slow and simple movements — first the fingers, forearms, shoulders, and then the whole body begins to revive. Then suddenly the arms, legs, body are connected to the complex movements involved. Part of the melody alternates with dance movements in repetition. With the change in the character of the melody and the acceleration of the pace, the dance becomes more and more intense and the end without tension.

Today, our distinguished president is SH.M.Mirziyoyev's attention to the National Art of dance, in particular to The Art of Khorezm dance, is great. A vivid proof of our opinion is the establishment of A Dance Academy branch, a dance boarding school in the Khorezm region, the holding of international dance festivals “dance magic” and “Lazgi” in Khiva every two years. This, of course, imposes a great responsibility not only on professional balletmakers, choreographers, but also on the music leaders of preschool educational organizations in preserving, developing and delivering our national dance art to the next generation.

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